

IMPORTANCE OF INSECT POLLINATION IN UZBEKISTAN AGRICULTURE: POLLINATOR DEPENDENT PRODUCTION ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *Animal pollination, primarily facilitated by diverse insect groups such as bees and hoverflies, is a crucial ecosystem service. It significantly impacts agricultural productivity and nutritional security, which are essential for human wellbeing. This study aimed to understand the significance of pollinator in the agricultural crop production in Uzbekistan. Analysing 65 crop systems, we found that approximately 64.6% are pollinator-dependent, with crops like almonds, apples, blueberries, and watermelons demonstrating varying degrees of reliance. Percentage contribution of total crop production was 17%. However, if excluding cereals, 27.8% of crop production was relied on pollinators. Vulnerability analysis indicated that a reduction in pollinator populations would significantly threaten agricultural production. Enhancing pollination service could boost agricultural yields and improve nutritional quality, benefiting consumer health. Therefore, protecting and enhancing pollination services and implementing sustainable agricultural practices are vital.*

Key words: *crop production, pollinator dependence, pollination service, honey bee, sustainability, food and nutrition security, ecological service.*

Introduction. Insect pollination is a critical component of agricultural productivity and ecosystem health. Approximately 75% of the world's major crops benefit from animal pollination, primarily by insects (Klein et al. 2007). Pollinated crops often produce more fruit and seeds, and the quality of these products is typically superior (Jung, 2008). For instance, strawberries pollinated by insects are larger and have better shape and colour (Klatt et al., 2014). Similarly, insect-pollinated apples are more symmetrical and of higher quality (Son and Jung, 2021).

A wide range of crops relies on insect pollination, including many fruits, vegetables, nuts, and oilseeds. Fruit crops such as apples, almonds, cherry, plum and blueberries are heavily depending on insect pollinators (Somerville, 1999a,b). The economic value of insect pollination is substantial. Gallai et al. (2009) estimated that insect pollination contributes approximately \$235 billion to \$577 billion annually to the global economy. In Korea, Jung (2008) and Jung and Shin (2022) reported one quarter of crop production is related to insect pollination, with economic contribution of approximately \$5.5 billion. In addition to its economic benefits, insect pollination plays a crucial role in maintaining biodiversity supporting vegetation structures, and sustaining food webs and wildlife. Proper reproduction and genetic diversity of plants, facilitated by insect pollination, enhances ecosystem resilience and stability (Potts et al., 2010).

Crop production and yield are influenced by various factors, including soil nutrients, environmental and climatic conditions, pests, and diseases. Among these, pollinators play a crucial yet often underappreciated role (Garibaldi et al., 2016). While not all crops require pollinators for cross-pollination, many do, to varying extents. Some plants are wind-pollinated, while others depend on pollinators.

Although there are numerous pollinators, insects, particularly honey bees, are considered the primary workforce in pollination. Additionally, wild solitary bees significantly contribute to

crop production (Garibaldi et al., 2013). Important groups of pollinators are honey bees (*Apis mellifera*), bumblebees, wild solitary bees, other solitary bees. Hover flies, other flies, butterflies, moths and beetles. Honeybees and some bumblebees are commercially available and possible to manage but other bees are mostly considered as wild bees. Honey bees are the most widely managed pollinators and are essential for many commercial crops of larger areas (Delaplane & Mayer, 2000). Bumblebees are effective at pollinating tomatoes and peppers, which require buzz pollination (Morandin et al., 2001; Ercan and Onus, 2003). Flies are crucial for crops like carrots, onions, and some berries (Orford et al., 2015).

Numerous studies have been conducted to estimate the contribution of pollinators to the national economy. However, pollinators not only enhance economic value but also improve the health and well-being of the population by increasing the yield and production of nutrient-rich crops (Smith et al. 2015; Ghosh and Jung, 2016, 2018, 2024).

Understanding the dependency on pollinators for nutrient supply is essential. Several factors, including crop yield, dietary diversity, and the impact of agroecosystems, influence the measurement of pollinators' contribution to providing essential nutrients. A detailed understanding of the role of pollinators can inform policies aimed at conserving pollinator populations and ensuring a stable nutrient supply. This comprehensive approach can help in framing policies that promote both the conservation of pollinators and the nutritional well-being of the population. As we do not have enough information on crop-pollinator networks in Uzbekistan, we had analysed the crop production data relative to the pollinator dependency. This can be used as the basic data for further crop yield improvement using relevant pollination techniques and services.

Methods. Agricultural production data were obtained from FAO stat based on year 2022 of Uzbekistan (Table 1). Data comprises the kinds of crop, area cultivated (ha), yield per hectare, and national production (t). Based on the degree of dependency, crops can be classified into four categories: little (1-10%), modest (10-40%), great (40-90%), and essential (>90%) dependency on pollinators (Klein et al 2007). Also we added the pollinator-dependency for a few more crops such as pistachio and safflower seeds.

Table 1. Agricultural crops cultivation and production data of Uzbekistan in 2022 adopted from FAO statistics (FAOSTAT) relative to the pollinator dependencies

Pollinator dependency	Crop	Area (ha)	Yield (100g/ha)	Production (t)
No	Barley	99238	12439	123447.1
	Carrot and turnips	47023	832780	3915983
	Cereals n.e.c.	4842	24101	11669.39
	Lentils, dry	1111	9587	1065.14
	Maize	62772	104572	656414.4
	Millet	27689	28000	77531
	Oats	836	5885	492
	Other pulses n.e.c.	11773	37403	44033.52
	Peas, dry	1235	28118	3472.33
	Peas, green	817	59183	4837.04
	Rice	46322	77533	359147.1
	Sorghum	12130	13860	16812.21
	Walnuts, in shell	5102	94426	48179.68
	Wheat	1257071	49878	6270059
Little	Safflower seed	8624	6824	5885.25

	Chick peas dry	5023	27561	13844.43
	Chillies and peppers, dry (Capsicum spp., Pimenta spp.), raw	4954	45767	22672.91
	Chillies and peppers, green (Capsicum spp. and Pimenta spp.)	897	759044	68108.82
	Grapes	113083	155688	1760559
	Groundnuts, excluding shelled	1372	166229	22801.57
	Leeks and other alliaceous vegetables	831	87995	7311.66
	Lemons and limes	1577	67241	10601.49
	Onions and shallots, dry (excluding dehydrated)	33710	360231	1214349
	Other beans, green	556	122825	6823.95
	Other citrus fruit, n.e.c.	628	168771	10601.49
	Pepper (Piper spp.), raw	324	6544	211.83
	Persimmons	3426	235641	80723.81
	Pomelos and grapefruits	141	187419	2635.93
	Potatoes	109110	315573	3443224
	Tangerines, mandarins, clementines	116	116539	1347.17
	Tomatoes	64226	341162	2191153
Modest	Broad beans, horse beans dry	2746	57137	15692.24
	Broad beans, horse beans green	582	86700	5041.73
	Currants	84	195302	1637.84
	Eggplants (aubergines)	9183	222037	203888.8
	Figs	878	339940	29844.18
	Rape or colza seed	1822	7071	1288.41
	Sesame seed	7633	18654	14239.09
	Soya beans	12385	28150	34862.38
	Strawberries	783	134111	10500.9
	Sunflower seed	8279	50943	42174.07
	Seed Cotton	1026858	34091	3500680
Great	Almond	2706	114366	30945.06
	Apple	122459	107239	1313232.89
	Apricot	39332	114731	451262.8
	Blueberries	94	70811	667.59
	Buckwheat	15	8000	12
	Cherries	15241	142289	216866.9
	Cucumbers and gherkins	27489	329001	904390
	Peaches and nectarines	20044	105745	211955
	Pears	7292	161210	117546.3
	Plums and sloes	15040	118087	177602.3
	Quinces	4044	224734	90871.09
	Raspberries	--	--	900
	Sour cherries	7051	114611	80809.04
Essential	Watermelons	41922	343345	1439370
Unknown	Artichokes	122	317500	3862.23
	Hazelnuts, in shell	3000	12426	3727.86
	Lettuce and chicory	336	146048	4909.67

Linseed	3000	3333	1000
Olives	139	8644	119.94
Pistachios, in shell	1046	3767	394
Rye	142	98375	1394
Cabbage	13586	579787	787670.3
Sugar beet	67	295373	1979

Figure 1. Agricultural crop profiles of Uzbekistan in 2022, relative to the pollinator-dependency categories

Results and Discussion. Table 1 provides that out of 65 crop systems, approximately 42 crops, i.e. about 64.6%, are pollinator dependent. Within these pollinator-dependent crops, 17 belong to the category of little pollinator dependence. This group includes crops such as chickpeas, chilies, groundnuts, beans, lemons, and limes. Eleven crops fall into the modest pollinator dependent group, while thirteen crops are classified under the great pollinator dependent group. Notably, only one crop, watermelon, is categorized as essential pollinator dependent. Examples of modest pollinator dependent crops include broad beans, horse beans, soybeans, figs, eggplants, strawberries, and cotton seeds. In contrast, many fruits, such as almonds, apples, blueberries, cucumbers and gherkins, peaches and nectarines, pears, plums, quinces, and raspberries, exhibit a high degree of pollinator dependence.

From a nutritional perspective, cereals serve as staples, primarily providing carbohydrates. Pulses are a significant source of protein, while vegetables and fruits offer fiber, minerals, vitamins, and numerous biofunctional compounds. Many of these vegetables and fruits, along with some legumes such as various beans, including soybeans, rely on pollinators. Consequently, the nutrients derived from these crops are also dependent on pollinators. The decline in pollinator populations could pose a threat to these agricultural systems and negatively impact the nutritional status of the population.

It is also noteworthy that some crops classified under the unknown dependency group might require pollinators for cross-pollination. However, the extent of this dependency is not yet known, leading to their placement in the unknown category.

Figure 1 depicts the agricultural crop profiles of Uzbekistan in 2022, relative to the pollinator-dependency categories. When examining the yield and cultivation area of these crop systems, the largest cultivation areas are occupied by crops that are independent of pollinators (Figure 1). Conversely, the cultivation area for pollinator-dependent crops is comparatively smaller (Figure 1). However, the yield scenario is quite the opposite (Figure 1). The average yield of pollinator-dependent crops is higher than that of non-pollinator-dependent crops. This higher yield is reflected in the production volume of these crops.

Table 2 illustrates the effects of optimum pollinator and reduced pollinator scenario on the crop production relative to the pollinator dependency categories. By incorporating pollinator dependency, we estimated the importance of animal pollinators for crop production. We found that 64% of crops are pollinator-dependent. These crops contribute 17% to total crop production. However, when cereals are excluded, 27.8% of crop production relies on pollinators.

Cereals, grasses, and other nut producing crops such as olives, dates, pistachios, walnuts, and some vegetable seeds are considered as wind-pollinating plants (Karimi and Zeraatkar, 2016). Generally, these plants are self-fertile, they can produce fruit from their own pollens. Natural wind pollination is dependent on the synchronization of the blooming of male and female plants or different cultivars, as well as meteorological conditions such as temperature, day length, wind intensity, and other environmental factors including water and soil quality. However, self-pollination alone often results in lower fruit set and yield, necessitating additional cross-pollination, where pollen is transferred from one tree or variety to another. Some varieties require cross-pollination more than others. In the recent years, increasing asynchrony between the flowering of male and female trees has been observed, attributed to climate change and global warming. Consequently, additional artificial pollination services or by other insect pollinators are required.

Table 3. Effects of optimum pollinator and reduced pollinator scenario on the crop production relative to the pollinator dependency categories

	Total production	PD P	Optimum P	%	Lower P	%
Essential	1439	1367	1713	119	984	68
Great	3597	2338	4065	113	2818	78
Modest	3859	965	4053	105	3538	92
Little	8862	443	8951	101	8715	98
No	11533	0	11533	100	11533	100
Unknown	805	0	805	100	805	100
All crop	30095	-	31120	103	28393	94
All PD crop	17757	5114	18782	106	16055	90

Proportion (%)	59.0	17.0
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Smith et al. (2015) demonstrated that declines in animal pollinators could lead to significant global health burdens, including increased rates of non-communicable diseases and micronutrient deficiencies. The decline in pollinators, particularly honeybees, in various regions threatens agricultural productivity and food security. Analyzing data from 60 crop systems across five continents from 1983-2013, the study found that honeybee population patterns positively correlated with crop yields of little, modest, and great pollinator-dependent crops, but negatively with essential pollinator-dependent crops (Ghosh and Jung, 2016). In Korea and India, increased yields in crops with medium pollination dependence were linked to rising honeybee hive numbers, while yield changes in essential pollinator-dependent crops appeared more influenced by socioeconomic conditions (Ghosh and Jung, 2016). Further investigation revealed that in Korea, pollinator-dependent crops contribute significantly to the supply of vitamins C and E, and iron, with a higher reliance on pollinators compared to the global average. The stable supply of these micronutrients over the past three decades highlights the critical role of pollination in ensuring nutritional security (Ghosh and Jung 2018). Similarly, In India, pollinator-dependent crops are significant sources of vitamins B7, B9, C, and K, despite their slower yield increase compared to non-pollinator-dependent crops, indicating the critical role of pollinators in enhancing nutritional quality (Ghosh and Jung, 2024). Given this significant role, it is essential to estimate the contribution of pollinators in Uzbekistan to understand their impact on national food and nutritional security. Planning for the conservation of both managed and wild bees is necessary to protect biodiversity and ensure a stable nutrient supply. Implementing pollinator-friendly habitat management practices in Uzbekistan could prevent negative impacts from pollinator loss and sustain crucial ecosystem services.

Conclusion. The analysis reveals that 64.6% of 65 studied crops are pollinator-dependent, highlighting the critical role of pollinators in agricultural productivity and nutrition. Pollinator declines could threaten food security and nutritional quality, as seen in the impact on crops providing essential vitamins and minerals in regions like Korea and India. Despite smaller cultivation areas, pollinator-dependent crops have higher yields, emphasizing their significance. To ensure food and nutritional security in Uzbekistan, further investigation is needed to figure out the contribution of pollinators to the nutrient supply of the country and to implement conservation strategies for both managed and wild bees.

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